

Evaluating Building Project Performance and Indoor Thermal Comfort in Nigerian Public Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract: This study assessed the performance and indoor thermal comfort of building projects in Nigeria public tertiary institutions. The study was delimited to public tertiary institutions in South-West Nigeria. To this end, a total of 180 sample were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. One state public tertiary intuition was selected from each state and 30 offices and staff were selected in each. Data was collected using a whirling/sling psychrometer and well-structured questionnaire. Measurements were taken 5 times between 10 - 3pm. The psychrometer was used to collect data on air temperature and relative humidity of the buildings and offices. Humidex was used to interpret the thermal comfort of the buildings. Result revealed that occupants experience discomfort and the level of discomfort increases significantly over time most especially between 12noon and 3pm. Building functionality is which is also a key factor in building performance is highlighted in the study as many of the buildings suffers from proper ergonomic design principles, inadequate lighting, and uncomfortable seating arrangements need to be addressed to improve occupant comfort and productivity. Additionally, the satisfaction level regarding building maintenance falls below acceptable limits, emphasizing the need for improved upkeep and functionality. Hence, stakeholders providing building structures for public institutions should prioritize the implementation of measures to improve thermal comfort, address ergonomic design principles, and enhance maintenance practices.

Keywords: Building Performance, Thermal Comfort, Functionality, Amenities

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Introduction

Physical structures of every organization remain an integral part of the organization because it helps the occupants to perform as effective as they should and subsequently helps organizations achieve their goal. Building project performance has is a complex and multifaceted concept that requires a comprehensive approach which might. Turgut et al., (2020) perceived performance of building project in terms of quality, time, cost, safety, and sustainability, emphasizing the importance of achieving sustainability objectives in addition to meeting other project criteria. Their submission is rather encompassing and covers a range of criteria that must be declared for sustainability to be achieved. Additionally, building project performance has also been perceived as the extent to which a project meets its objectives in terms of cost, schedule, quality, and safety (Jia & Shen, 2011; Kumaraswamy and Chan, 2016). It is pertinent to point out the need for project managers to ensure that the objectives are in line with standard ethical practices while suggesting improvements where there is need (Tanko et al., 2018).

In contrasts, many Nigerian authors view building performance from the point of view of its effects on its occupants. This is based on the fact that irrespective of the objectives or requirements of the stakeholders, performance of building project should to a large extent be determined by its occupants and usage. The submission of Mahamid (2016) for instance revealed that building's users interact with its physical surroundings, work conditions, and neighbouring businesses can affect how well it performs. Furthermore, in the words of Chendo and Obi (2015), building performance refers to the physical performance of a building as a whole or in its component elements. From a more holistic approach Gargate and Momaya, (2018) believes that project managers must design building projects goals that are motivated by comfort, safety, health, and other factors in order to measure the performance of buildings. Infact, historically, the concept of Building Performance has been applied to aspects such as indoor air quality, fire safety, thermal efficiency, and noise control. These individual criteria are crucial in determining how effectively the building meets its functional requirements at a micro-level (De Wilde, 2019; Jin, et al., 2019).

From stakeholders' perspective, Wu, Liu and Le (2017) opined that building project performance is the degree to which the project has met or exceeded the expectations of its stakeholders in terms of delivering a high-quality building that meets their needs, within budget and on time. Similarly, Kangari and Schmitz (2018) submits that the sustainability or performance of building project performance equates the degree to which the project has met or exceeded the requirements of its stakeholders in terms of functionality, quality, cost, schedule, and safety. In other words they believe that stakeholders hold very significant position in influencing building performance.

According to Miller (2009), comfort is a sense of physical or psychological ease, often characterized as a lack of hardship. Thermal ccomfort involves both physical and psychological experience; the physical experience can be directly linked to the relationship between the body and the physical conditions of the environment which essentially include the air temperature and relative humidity while the psychological experience is the memory such experiences leave behind. In other words, the weather or climatic conditions of the workplace environment constitute the major aspects of the physical environment that affects the thermophysiological comfort of workers. Radostina (2017) perceived thermal comfort

to be an aspect of human comfort that is that is preconditioned by the functioning of the thermoregulatory system of the body and its reactions to the temperature of the surrounding air, the activity performed, and the used clothing insulation.

Thermal comfort here includes factors such as apparent temperature, clothing nature, and perspiration. Salopek and Skenderi (2010) also noted that thermophysiological comfort is related to the heat balance maintained between the body, environment, and textile. In other words, it takes account of the environmental condition the physical structure of the building presents to its occupants. Other factors that can influence thermophysiological comfort include radiant heat (hot surface), gender, health status, activity level, etc. Hence, the process of correctly judging thermal comfort is a cognitive process involving human physical, psychological, and other conditions. Discomfort mainly results from the build-up of sweat on the skin and insufficient heat loss during overheating in hot environments and exercise (Fohr, Couton, and Treguier, 2002).

The physical infrastructure of public educational institutions in Nigeria are encountering various obstacles that hinder their ability to provide standards, which is crucial for enhancing organizational growth and overall achievement of the institution evident in academic performance of students and quality of research. This physical structure has substantial influence on the performance and effectiveness of the inhabitants most especially staff of the institutions. For instance, it has been observed that that the supply of electricity has not been what it should in many of the public tertiary institutions. This leaves the staff at the mercy of the condition the environment offers. It is on this note Isa and Yusoff (2015) pointed that the performance of physical facilities in most Nigerian tertiary institutions is not appealing which general have effects on the level of productivity, general performance and global ranking of most institutions (Mukhtar et al., 2021). Even though there is a mirage of factors that could influence these conditions, workplace environmental parameters like air temperature and relative humidity could play a significant role and this would be the basis for predicting the performance and level of thermal comfort of the buildings.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study assesses the building performance of the public tertiary institutions in Nigeria by:

- i. predicting the thermal comfort of the building projects
- ii. examining the occupant satisfaction towards the building projects.

Scope of the Study

This scope of this study is limited to examining building performance through occupant satisfaction to building amenities, overall comfort and functionality. The thermal comfort of the buildings is determined by measuring the air temperature (AT) and relative humidity (RH) using a whirling or sling psychrometer, an instrument that collects the air temperature and relative humidity simultaneously. Geographically, the study covers selected state public tertiary institutions in South-West of Nigeria. South-West Nigeria comprises of six states (Lagos, Ondo, Ogun, Osun, Oyo and Ekiti). The State universities selected are: Lagos State University, Ojo; Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye; Osun State University, Osogbo; Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti; Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko; Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso.

Methodology

The study is a descriptive research design. The population of the study is the staff of public tertiary institutions in South-West of Nigeria. Data was obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The sample procedure includes that of the objective measurement on thermal comfort and survey on occupant satisfaction. A total of 180 samples were selected

using multi-stage sampling technique. This was obtained at two different stages. At the first stage, 6 state owned public tertiary institutions were selected using the purposive sampling technique (1 state public institution from each state). At the second stage, stratified sampling technique was used to select 30 samples from each public institution with the consideration of sex and job specification (academic/non-academic).

Instruments

The study made use of both well-structured questionnaire and whirling psychrometer to obtain the data used in the study. The whirling/sling psychrometer is made up of two standard Thermometers (Dry Bulb Thermometer and Wet Bulb Thermometer) mounted on a frame with a handle. The Wet Bulb Thermometer has a moistened piece of cloth wrapped about the bulb (See Appendix). The instrument was whirled around for several minutes and then the results were read and recorded. The Dry Bulb Thermometer measures the air temperature while the wet bulb thermometer measures relative humidity by calculating the temperature difference through the cooling of moisture from the dampened piece of cloth. The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A & B), section A contained questions on the bio-data of the respondents, section B was designed to collect data on the occupants building performance satisfaction (building amenities, comfort and functionality).

Method of Data Collection

Readings were taken in the offices of the selected samples. This was done between 10am and 3pm at one-hour intervals (10:30am, 11:30am, 12:30am, 1:30pm, 2:30pm). It, therefore, gave a total of 5 readings in each office. The readings were taken at this period of the day because in the morning, the weather condition still feels bearable and with lesser heating while it does not extend to 3pm because many of the occupants would have plan leaving their offices. Readings were repeated for the selected 180 offices which gave a total of 900 readings in all. Data were collected with the aid of 10 well trained research assistants. Data were analyzed using Humidex (See Appendix) and descriptive statistics, while results were presented in charts.

Ethical Consideration

An ethical research approval and permit was obtained from ethical research committee at each University’s Centre for Research and Development before data was collected.

Results: Building Performance (Thermal Comfort)

Table 1: Humidex of Building Offices Thermal Comfort between 10am and 11am

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort	<i>f</i>	%	Mean AT	Mean RH
20 – 29	No Discomfort	0	0.0	28.1°C	78%
30 – 39	Some Discomfort	159	88.3		
40 – 45	Great Discomfort	21	11.7		
46 +	Dangerous	0	0.0		
Total		180	100.0		

In Table 1, predicting the thermal comfort of the building between 10am and 11am, it was revealed that 88.3% of the selected offices will be have some level of discomfort in their offices between 10am and 11am while 11.7% of the offices were predicted to be provide some level of great discomfort between 10am and 11am while none of the offices will provide a dangerous indoor environment to occupants. In other words, the thermal comfort of the building’s offices between 10am and 11am is quite satisfying with a very low level of discomfort.

Table 2: Humidex of Building Offices Thermal Comfort between 11am and 12noon

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort	<i>f</i>	%	Mean AT	Mean RH
20 – 29	No Discomfort	0	0.0	28.4°C	79%
30 – 39	Some Discomfort	115	63.9		
40 – 45	Great Discomfort	65	36.2		
46 +	Dangerous	0	0.0		
Total		180	100.0		

Table 2 revealed that the thermal comfort of the building between 11am and 12 noon will make 63.9% of the occupants of the offices experience some level of discomfort, while 36.2% of the offices were predicted to be provide some level of great discomfort between 10am and 11am. Also, none of the offices will provide a dangerous indoor environment to occupants. Although there is an increase in the offices that provides some level of great discomfort, the mean value revealed that majority only experience some discomfort.

Table 3: Humidex of Building Offices Thermal Comfort between 12noon and 1pm

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort	<i>f</i>	%	Mean AT	Mean RH
20 – 29	No Discomfort	0	0.0	29.1°C	78%
30 – 39	Some Discomfort	60	33.3		
40 – 45	Great Discomfort	120	66.7		
46 +	Dangerous	0	0.0		
Total		180	100.0		

Result presented in Table 3 on the level of thermal comfort of the building between 12 noon and 1pm shows 33.3% of the occupants of the offices experience some level of discomfort, while 66.7% of the offices were predicted to provide a great discomfort between 12noon and 1pm. Based on the mean air temperature and relative humidity, majority of the offices falls in the great discomfort category. Hence, there is a build-up of heat in the buildings which has started creating some level of great discomfort to the occupants.

Table 4: Humidex of Building Offices Thermal Comfort between 1pm and 2pm

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort	<i>F</i>	%	Mean AT	Mean RH
20 – 29	No Discomfort	0	0.0	29.7°C	76%
30 – 39	Some Discomfort	33	18.3		
40 – 45	Great Discomfort	147	81.7		
46 +	Dangerous	0	0.0		
Total		180	100.0		

Table 4 showed that the level of great discomfort noticed in the offices increased significantly. This is evident as 81.7% of the offices become quite difficult for the occupants to stay in without making provisions for indoor weather modification resources. The level of some discomfort then drops to 18.3%. Overall, the mean air temperature 29.7°C and relative humidity 76% revealed that the buildings offices provide a great level of discomfort to its occupants.

Table 5: Humidex of Building Offices Thermal Comfort between 2pm and 3pm

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort	F	%	Mean AT	Mean RH
20 – 29	No Discomfort	0	0.0	30.2°C	74%
30 – 39	Some Discomfort	23	12.8		
40 – 45	Great Discomfort	157	87.2		
46 +	Dangerous	0	0.0		
Total		180	100.0		

Result in Table 5 revealed that only 12.8% of the offices exhibit some level of discomforts to its occupants while 87.2% of the offices provides a great level of discomfort to its occupants. In essence, the level of discomfort in the offices increased between 2pm and 3pm. In other words, if the occupants continued to stay in the offices at the time without giving attention to making the office habitable it could have effect on his/her productivity or health. Overall, majority of the offices at this time have a low level of performance.

II. Building Performance Satisfaction

Figure 1: Mean Level of Satisfaction of Building Functionality and Amenities

Figure 1 on the mean level of satisfaction on building functionality in the public institutions revealed that the buildings layout has the highest level of satisfaction which means the offices have satisfying room sizes and spaces. Closely followed is the safety of the buildings and utilities. The level of accessibility of the buildings was also quite satisfying and the ventilation. However, many of the buildings were not designed ergonomics principles which as proper lightning, comfortable seating etc. Similarly, the level of satisfaction on the maintenance of the building is below acceptable limits which are not healthy for the performance of the building.

Figure 2: Mean Level of Satisfaction of Building Comfort

In Figure 2 the mean level of satisfaction on building comfort in the public institutions revealed the air quality in the building provides a high level of satisfaction to the occupants. Similarly, occupants have some level of control such as temperature control, lightning adjustments, and windows to enhance comfort based on their needs. However, thermal comfort and the visual comfort of the occupants were not very satisfying.

Discussion

The analysis conducted on the thermal comfort conditions in the building reveals significant concerns regarding the level of discomfort experienced by occupants. The majority of selected offices experience some level of discomfort, with a notable portion facing a higher level of discomfort. While the conditions do not reach a level of danger, they still negatively impact the well-being and comfort of occupants. It becomes apparent that the discomfort experienced by office occupants increases significantly. The majority of offices become challenging for occupants to stay in without implementing measures to modify the indoor weather (Ye et al., 2005). This suggests a persistent issue that needs to be addressed to improve the overall comfort and satisfaction of the occupants. These finding highlights that of Anrejiova et al. (2012) who found that when the temperature exceeds 26°C and the relative humidity surpasses 65%, the indoor environment becomes uncomfortable. In tandem with this

The findings highlight the importance of implementing strategies to enhance thermal comfort in the building. Improving ventilation, implementing shading measures, and ensuring effective temperature control systems are essential in creating a more comfortable indoor environment. By addressing discomfort issues, building owners and occupants can promote optimal conditions for work or living, leading to improved well-being, satisfaction, and productivity (Bluyseen et al., 2016). Neglecting to address these discomfort issues can have negative consequences on occupant productivity and health (Sakellaris et al., 2023). It is crucial for building owners to prioritize the implementation of appropriate measures to create a space that prioritizes occupant comfort and fosters a conducive environment.

Furthermore, in terms of building functionality, the layout of the buildings receives high satisfaction ratings from occupants. They find the room sizes and spaces to be satisfying overall. The safety features and availability of utilities also receive positive feedback, indicating that occupants feel secure and have access to necessary resources. The accessibility of the buildings and the ventilation systems are considered satisfactory, suggesting that occupants can easily navigate the buildings and have sufficient airflow. However, one notable area of concern is the lack of proper ergonomic design principles in many buildings. This includes inadequate lighting and uncomfortable seating

arrangements, which may impact occupant comfort and productivity. Additionally, the satisfaction level regarding building maintenance falls below acceptable limits. This implies that improvements are needed to ensure the proper upkeep and functionality of the buildings (Moncef, 2018). Moving to building comfort, the analysis indicates that occupants are highly satisfied with the air quality within the buildings. This suggests that measures are in place to ensure good indoor air quality, which is crucial for occupant health and well-being. Furthermore, occupants have some level of control over their comfort, including the ability to adjust temperature, lighting, and access windows for ventilation. This level of control contributes positively to occupant comfort. However, the findings also reveal that there are areas where satisfaction levels are not particularly high. Thermal comfort, which refers to the perceived temperature satisfaction, and visual comfort, which encompasses factors like lighting quality and glare, receive lower satisfaction ratings. This indicates the need for improvements in these areas to enhance the overall comfort experience for occupants.

Conclusion

Conclusively, the study highlights significant concerns regarding the building performance from thermal comforts and the level of satisfaction on some building performance indicators. It is evident that occupants experience discomfort and the level of discomfort increases significantly over time. Implementing strategies to enhance thermal comfort, such as improving ventilation, shading measures, and temperature control systems, is crucial to create a more comfortable indoor environment. Building functionality is which is also a key factor in building performance is highlighted in the study as many of the buildings suffers from proper ergonomic design principles, inadequate lighting, and uncomfortable seating arrangements need to be addressed to improve occupant comfort and productivity. Additionally, the satisfaction level regarding building maintenance falls below acceptable limits, emphasizing the need for improved upkeep and functionality. It is therefore recommended that stakeholders providing building structures for public institutions should prioritize the implementation of measures to improve thermal comfort, address ergonomic design principles, and enhance maintenance practices. This will contribute to creating a more comfortable and functional environment, promoting occupant well-being, satisfaction, and productivity.

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Appendix

Sling/Whirling Psychrometer

		Relative Humidity (%)																
		100%	95%	90%	85%	80%	75%	70%	65%	60%	55%	50%	45%	40%	35%	30%	25%	20%
Temperature (°C)	21°C	29	29	28	27	27	26	26	24	24	23	23	22					
	22°C	31	29	29	28	28	27	26	26	24	24	23	23					
	23°C	33	32	32	31	30	29	28	27	27	26	25	24	23				
	24°C	35	34	33	33	32	31	30	29	28	28	27	26	26	25			
	25°C	37	36	35	34	33	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	27	26			
	26°C	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	31	29	28	28	27			
	27°C	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	28		
	28°C	43	42	41	41	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	29	28		
	29°C	46	45	44	43	42	41	39	38	37	36	34	33	32	31	30		
	30°C	48	47	46	44	43	42	41	40	38	37	36	35	34	33	31	31	
	31°C	50	49	48	46	45	44	43	41	40	39	38	36	35	34	33	31	
	32°C	52	51	50	49	47	46	45	43	42	41	39	38	37	36	34	33	
	33°C	55	54	52	51	50	48	47	46	44	43	42	40	38	37	36	34	
	34°C	58	57	55	53	52	51	49	48	47	45	43	42	41	39	37	36	
	35°C		58	57	56	54	52	51	49	48	47	45	43	42	41	38	37	
	36°C			58	57	56	54	53	51	50	48	47	45	43	42	40	38	
	37°C					58	57	55	53	51	50	49	47	45	43	42	40	
38°C							57	56	54	52	51	49	47	46	43	42	40	
39°C									56	54	53	51	49	47	45	43	41	
40°C										57	54	52	51	49	47	44	43	

Humidex	Degree of Discomfort
20 - 29	No discomfort
30 - 39	Some discomfort
40 - 45	Great discomfort; avoid exertion
46 +	Dangerous; possible heat stroke

Humidex (Humidity Index)

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